

Iberoamerican Journal of Entrepreneurship and Small Business

ENTREPRENEURIAL RESPONSES OF COPING CATASTROPHIC EVENTS AND CRISIS SITUATIONS

Vânia Maria Jorge Nassif¹
Dennys Eduardo Rossetto²
Edmundo Inácio Júnior³

DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.14211/regepe.v9i4.2010>

Translator: Eliane Herrero Lopes

We keep on searching for answers to the dilemmas faced by entrepreneurs as a result of adverse events, often unpredictable and uncontrollable, such as attacks, epidemics, pandemics, and natural disasters, environmental or geological, all responsible for driving crisis situations.

IJESB - Iberoamerican Journal of Entrepreneurship and Small Business (REGEPE - Revista de Empreendedorismo e Gestão de Pequenas Empresas), is always attentive in updating its readers with reflections of the moment and having as inspiration a recent call from the Journal "Entrepreneurship: Theory and Practice", in which they encourage the submission of papers that contribute to the understanding of different entrepreneurial responses to catastrophic events and crisis situations brings, from the suggestions of this call and the previous literature indicated, some insights into scenarios with epidemic and catastrophic events, as in the current context generated by the COVID-19 pandemic, given the impact caused on entrepreneurial business and the need for entrepreneurial responses to cope with it.

In the IJESB's previous editorials, we discussed similar issues in order to investigate whether entrepreneurs and small companies were prepared to deal with

¹ Docente do Programa de Pós-graduação em Administração - PPGA (UNINOVE), São Paulo (Brasil).
Editora chefe da Regepe. Email: editorialregep@gmail.com

² Associated Professor of Global Innovation and Entrepreneurship, SKEMA Business School (Brazil, China, France, South Africa, USA), Université Côte d'Azur (GREDEG). Email: dennyseduardo.rossetto@skema.edu

³ Docente na Faculdade de Ciências Aplicadas (FCA) da Universidade Estadual de Campinas (UNICAMP), São Paulo (Brasil). Email: edmundo.inacio@fca.unicamp.br

contextual adversities (Nassif et al., 2020a). This discussion is important since crisis situations and unexpected events alter the path of business leading to difficulties, sometimes irreparable. In this sense, we sought to glimpse whether would be light at the end of the tunnel, in the post-COVID-19 context (Nassif et al., 2020b). These reflections showed complex perspectives for entrepreneurs due to the obscurity and uncertainty imposed by the current situation, aggravated by the scarcity of both resources and contributory public policies.

Even though there are still no efficient answers to these questions, as researchers and scholars in the area of entrepreneurship, we take a risk and insist on the challenging task of looking for alternative solutions. In this editorial, we chose to address studies that emerge from the literature, portraying both scientific and empirically entrepreneurial actions in the face of complex, catastrophic, uncertain, unpredictable and impacting situations.

The COVID-19 pandemic is promoting epidemiological and health repercussions on a global scale, in addition to social, economic, political, technological and cultural impacts. This kind of phenomenon has also happened around the world in the past, with other epidemics and disasters that changed the course of history. Therefore, we can count several examples that culminated in the undoing or discontinuation of businesses, populations, cities, countries and even continents.

During the 14th century, the bubonic plague - historically the cause of the Black Death - decimated half the population of Europe according to some estimates (Barata, 1987; Rosen, 1994). Cholera is still considered a pandemic today, due to its epidemic cycles, resurging from time to time with a devastating context (Rosen, 1994). It is also important to mention the Spanish Flu (1918), which influenced cultural practices and governmental rules all over the world to fight infectious diseases for many years (Silveira, 2005).

At the end of the 18th century, common belief was rooted in the idea that health problems and diseases were phenomena that affected society, demanding attention from the community (Martelli, 1997). The emergence of AIDS, for example, triggered

a complex series of manifestations, which were mostly associated with political, economic and scientific beliefs, customs, prejudices and interests (Queiroz, 2004).

Environmental and ecological accidents or disasters, on the other hand, make it clear that government responses, or even civil society, prioritize productivity, with a focus on economic growth, not ensuring the quality of the environment and population health (Pott & Estrela, 2017).

Motivated by the pressure from stakeholders on how companies should use natural resources and how this use would be communicated to society, some requirements regarding environmental issues became part of the planning of organizational strategies (Gray & Bebbington, 2001).

Thus, tragedies experienced both in the world and in Brazil provided unusual experiences with their specificities. According to Mata-Lima, Alvino-Borba, Pinheiro, Mata-Lima and Almeida (2013), disasters expose the cumulative effects of decisions (individual and/or collective), triggering environmental and socio-economic. This process is likely to come from material damage to the survival of human lives, in addition to spreading diseases and the degradation of the population's conditions.

Entrepreneurs' experiences around the world, in the post-disaster moments, showed that the recovery of the business environment is slower in the context of crisis, as stated by Mel, Mckenzie and Woodruff (2010), when analyzing the impacts of the tsunamis that reached Sri Lanka in 2004. Moreover, Fong and Luttmmer (2007) concluded the same in relation to hurricanes Katrina and Rita in the United States in 2005.

Zissimopoulos and Karoly (2010), dealing with the aforementioned disasters, in the USA, state that people need to change attitudes and behaviors since autonomous work and entrepreneurial activities can contribute to the recovery of the local economy, especially in the case of evacuees who return to their homes and communities after the catastrophic event. For those authors, although a job without ties to companies may represent a low level of employment and wages, it is capable

of creating opportunities to start something new, thus contributing to the economic recovery.

Data from the World Bank and United Nations (2010) showed the negative effect of catastrophic events or crises on the economic growth of underdeveloped regions, due to the precarious structure of their economies, the fragile social capital and the difficulty of raising financial resources to face emerging situations.

In Brazil, devastating tragedies have profoundly affected the environment, the population and also business. Nelson and Lima (2020) report the disaster in the Córrego d'Antas, in Nova Friburgo / Rio de Janeiro, in 2011, highlighting the importance of the local society to overcome the tragedy. Another example is the rupture of the tailings dam of the mining company Samarco, in 2015, which flooded houses in Bento Rodrigues district, in Mariana, central region of Minas Gerais. The disaster directly affected local businesses, such as the activity of farmers and fishermen, in addition to interruption of hosting services and mineral production, impacting the community socially and economically, which still seeks for recovering (Lacaz, Porto, & Pinheiro, 2017). Recently, we faced the tragedy of Brumadinho in Minas Gerais, in 2019, which caused symbolic, cultural and economic losses, in addition to multiple disruptions in local infrastructure and family businesses (Freitas, Barcellos, Asmus, Silva, & Xavier, 2019).

In spite of different reasons, which caused disasters and consequently tragedies, the community involved in the process is affected by different risks of economic, health, survival and, above all, related to emotional and affective issues. In this sense, some social practices such as solidarity and reciprocity, among others, raise collective emotions that could create uncertainty and insecurity, affecting survival actions, especially with regard to professional activities, and changing the social organization and the community's operations (Farny, Kibler, & Down, 2018).

On the other hand, according to Borges, Ferreira and Rover (2017), despite tragedies, disasters, and crises, companies, in a non-preventive but reactive way, end up finding ways to create or improve their projects even after accidents. These measures aim only at reducing impacts, not inhibiting the occurrence of future accidents.

These reflections raised the need to understand the main findings in the literature on individual, organizational and society entrepreneurial responses, capable of contributing to coping with crisis situations or catastrophic events.

Therefore, we present a brief review of this context while presenting the articles of this edition.

Individual entrepreneurial responses for catastrophic events and crisis situations

Davidsson and Gordon (2016) illuminate some possible ways of coping with crises, mainly of an economic nature, questioning whether entrepreneurs give up or continue their business. According to the authors, a macroeconomic crisis can trigger alternative responses among nascent entrepreneurs: they do not get involved, lag behind or seek compensation and adaptation. Thus, some entrepreneurs' labels, such as persistent (Hoang & Gimeno, 2010) and resilient (Bullough, Renko, & Myatt, 2014), explain their survival and the ability to overcome obstacles, responding positively to crises. It is worth mentioning that resilience, associated with greater flexibility and adaptability of younger actors were analyzed with the founders of businesses that survived difficult circumstances, through intelligent, economic and adaptive strategies and tactics (Baker & Nelson, 2005; Sarasvathy, 2008).

In the same approach, Smallbone, Kitching, Kasperova and Xheneti (2013) sought answers from small companies and the implications for their recovering in the post-crisis period, between 2008 and 2009, in the United Kingdom. The authors explain that small companies initially focused on drawing medium and long-term perspectives creating assertive strategies. They thus identified that the founders' resilient behavior and learning in the face of crisis were essential attributes to overcoming difficulties and adapting to a new context, all based on their experiences.

In their study, Williams and Shepherd (2016) sought answers in the face of the suffering experienced by local entrepreneurs in Haiti, after the 2010 earthquake, pointing out that part of the survey respondents, even in precarious and very difficult situations, identified potential opportunities. Therefore, they looked for key resources to restart their business, through simple and objective actions.

It is important to point that events resulting from disasters and/or job losses always account for threats to human well-being and lives, as they bring suffering and can lead entrepreneurs to rock bottom, damaging them both cognitively and emotionally. Even so, there are those who manage to "reverse the game", turning the

experience into learning gained to undertake new attempts and managing to recover (Shepherd & Williams, 2018).

In a hostile crisis context, with a high level of adversity, the study by Bullough and Renko (2013) revealed that the entrepreneurs surveyed in Afghanistan due to strong beliefs in personal skills, the search for self-efficacy, resilience and discernment. Those individuals managed to trace alternative paths in order to restart their lives.

Corroborating these findings, Kwong, Chuang, Manzoor and Rashid (2019) examined entrepreneurs displaced from Pakistan, in a time of war and conflict, pointing that, even in adversity, they managed to find different ways to adapt to the new order. This was reached with the use of bricolage to reestablish previous businesses, and open fronts for the development of new ventures in the host location.

Although part of the literature on the relationship between disasters and entrepreneurship focuses on making post-crisis responses, the background to entrepreneurial behavior and its connection to past and future crises remain untapped (Muñoz, Kimmitt, Kibler, & Farny, 2019).

In an exploratory study, at two different times - before and after the eruptions of the Calbuco volcano (2015 and 2016) in Chile - Muñoz et al. (2009) found as results four attributes that explain the antecedents of the entrepreneurs' performance and the introduction of new activities, in a context of continuous threat. The attributes are: (1) preparation, which allows entrepreneurs to understand possible reactions to disasters under specific conditions imposed by the events; (2) development of resilience as a consequence of preparation in a context of continuous threats, which contributes greatly to "jumping forward" (Doern, Williams & Vorley 2019), after the crisis. This attribute allows entrepreneurs to reflect on the needs to rebuild their enterprises, or to recover and to seek new opportunities; (3) and (4) understanding how micro businesses can support the development of infrastructure in a community, consequently compensating for the difficulties of the international, national and regional businesses, before and after a crisis event .

In this edition, based on the theme discussed above, we take the opportunity to present a text with relevant contributions, such as the perspective in "Impact Business: A Concept in Construction", by Edgard Barki, Juliana Rodrigues and Graziella Maria Comini. These authors identify the role, limits and challenges of

conceptualizing impact business and, through a theoretical essay, discuss the different approaches to adding socio-environmental value by companies. The article starts from a view of compensating for externalities negative effects until the insertion in the organizational strategy of new actors in the impact business ecosystem.

The article by Gilberto Sarfati, Thomaz Martins and Gabriel Akel Abrahão, “Confrontations between the founding partners: how do entrepreneurs overcome conflicts?”, addresses team conflicts experiences, which cause negative impacts on organizational performance, capable of leading to company mortality. The results of that research also warn that operational conflicts, evolved to affective, due to differences in the process of giving and receiving feedback, and/or how distrust between partners, can lead to the dissolution of a company.

Cristiane Krüger and Lucas Feksa Ramos researched “Entrepreneurial Behavior, based on Behavioral Characteristics and Entrepreneurial Intention”, pointing out that traditional methods of evaluating entrepreneurial behavior carry a degree of uncertainty and subjectivity, with numerous independent and uncontrollable variables. In addition, the authors highlighted fuzzy modeling, contributing to the understanding of entrepreneurial behavior.

The research by Tatiane Brum de Oliveira Reis and Amarolinda Iara da Costa Zanela Klein, developed in a non-conflicting context and far from being considered a crisis environment, brings some important answers to entrepreneurs on overcoming difficulties and improving skills through practices, search for information and attention to management models.

In addition to individual entrepreneurial responses, resulting from catastrophic events and crisis situations, we must also consider the organizational and entrepreneurs’ arising from society as following.

Organizational entrepreneurial responses to catastrophic events and crisis situations

Continuing the previous reasoning, and rescuing the main findings of the literature about entrepreneurial responses in the organizational level in times of crisis situations and catastrophic events, Williams, Gruber, Sutcliff, Shepherd and Zhao (2017) investigated the merger process between crisis and resilience, presenting an integrative model. The authors focused on key themes, regarding the capacities of

durability, organization and adjustments, as well as a feedback process of these experiences - situations perfectly applicable to the current context, due to the COVID-19 pandemic.

In the same context, Bacq, Geohegan, Josepy, Stevenson and Williams (2020) dedicated their studies to understand the use of entrepreneurial efforts to solve society's great challenges, such as frustrating the continuing threats from COVID-19 and other future evils. To this end, they describe a virtual blitz of ideas, capable of accelerating social entrepreneurial actions, and provide practical guidelines for their joint and coordinated use, through the unity of different organizations and community. Thus, they allow academic and professional institutions interested in replicating or adopting this approach to do so.

McDonald and Eisenhardt (2019) investigate the effective way of creating new business models and argue that many of them emerge in a process of side game, in which successful entrepreneurs do not consider their rival peers, but constantly observe them, making decisions based on business models after their "borrowed" trials or errors. Moreover, some aspects of the business model are left deliberately open or unfinished, in order to allow new groups of customers.

Geroski and Gregg (1996) addressed Organizational vulnerability in times of recession, because, at that time, some companies were severely affected by a collapse in demand. While less efficient organizations are expected to suffer the greatest upheavals, selection pressures can be short-sighted and penalize those that are facing only transitory difficulties. Based on data collected by a large-scale survey to identify the effects of the recent recession in United Kingdom leading companies, evidence suggests that those with exceptionally high growth rates before the recession are the most vulnerable to recession pressures.

Crisis situations and catastrophic events are, for the most part, unpredictable and uncontrollable. Battisti and Deakins (2017) sought to understand the role of dynamic organizational capabilities in post-disaster environments, such as after the series of earthquakes that hit the city of Christchurch, New Zealand, in 2010 and 2011. The authors developed a model based on quantitative data, indicating that a company's dynamic capabilities influence performance, as it experiences negative or positive effects on resource base. The data highlighted the importance of a proactive business posture and abilities to integrate external resources and recognizing new opportunities, in an environment characterized by high volatility and uncertainty.

Using mixed methods, combined with a qualitative analysis approach from the international media, Kuckertz et al. (2020) developed a quick response to the exogenous shock caused by the COVID-19 outbreak for innovative startups. The authors identified the adversities faced, illustrating how innovative startups deal with the crisis, using DIY responses. In addition, they present a set of suggestions and political actions to support these companies during the COVID-19.

Faced with such a global pandemic crisis, Dutta (2019) argue that specific problems are more or less evident triggers of the action of social entrepreneurs, added to the emergency needs. However, the same problems shared, salient and generally worthy of action, and may require solutions in fragmented communities, such as high levels of residential segregation by race and income. This research was conducted in the context of the foundation of defense and support organizations, in the health domain, in which the authors based their predictions.

Reymen et al. (2015) point out that companies are led to apply their strategic scope of activities and decision-making of effective decisions, increasing in the level of environmental uncertainty and the scarcity of resources, in times of great magnitude crisis, such as that of COVID-19. In difficult times, there is evidence of greater experimentation, lower performance and leaving the company, when stakeholders force the reduction of their strategic scope using causation, instead of expanding and effectuation.

On the other hand, Mithani (2020) argues that the existing organizational adaptation theories are inappropriate in the face of life-threatening events, such as natural disasters, terrorist attacks and pandemics, pointing, as an alternative way, the construction of theories based on research on resilience. In this sense, the author advances in understanding theoretically grounded of the changing nature of environmental challenges, and identify the most appropriate adaptation models for them. Thus, this perspective offers a renewed understanding of organizational adaptation, as well as guidelines for managers and a forum for political discussions, in order to more effectively address emerging environmental challenges.

Amid so many demands on entrepreneurial responses at the present time, Shepherd (2020) highlights fundamental premises, challenged by the COVID-19 pandemic, which may require a research basis, such as: attention to entrepreneurial mechanisms, capable of providing balance in around a new future; the focus on society's resilience, on the common (and not celebrated) heroes of entrepreneurship;

greater focus on business action (costs and benefits at a diverse set of stakeholders), on social innovations (which increase business efforts), on the well-being and self-regulation of entrepreneurs (whose failures are beyond their personal control).

Williams and Shepherd (2020) highlight the role of co-creators of new ventures and communities in post-catastrophic events, stressing that, despite all the volume of data available, companies face the same external shocks, differing only in the way of interpreting and reacting to institutional voids, which indicates limits for the generation of relationships between new ventures and their communities. Such findings contribute to the literature on community organizations, as they demonstrate how they reestablish communities and emerge within them at the same time.

We take the opportunity to introduce one of the articles in this edition in order to reinforce the insights of the brief literature review presented. The article is entitled “Entrepreneurial actions and public policies: an articulation to promote sport”, written by Denise Aparecida Hipólito Borges and Mônica Carvalho Alves Cappelle. The authors present ways of interpreting entrepreneurship in the public context, so that public managers can review their decisions, articulate entrepreneurial actions and formulate public policies aimed at promoting innovative actions of local development and coping with post-conflict situations-crisis. In addition, the authors also indicate the use of action research as a methodology for studies on entrepreneurship.

In extreme situations and catastrophic events, we often observe the displacement of immigrants, in search of the rebuilding of their lives. In this sense, Eduardo Picanço Cruz and Roberto Pessoa de Queiroz Falcão, based on data from Brazilians in Australia, Canada, Portugal and Estonia, present the article “Market Orientation for Small and Medium Enterprises of Brazilian Immigrants Abroad”. The results provide supporting evidence to the discussion about decision making in relation to the target audience attended by ethnic enterprise.

This context signals that we are in point of no return regarding digital transformation to which everyone needs to adapt. For the exercise of entrepreneurial activities, it is necessary, above all, the correct “Use of Digital Marketing”, according to Karoline Victorino, Jefferson Dobner Sordi, Manuela Albornoz Gonçalves, Luis Henrique Rauber and Nívia Maria Jahn. The authors conducted a research in a technological park and observed how strategic actions and digital marketing tools can promote new businesses and, consequently, digital inclusion, in activating local economies and in post-crisis recovery. Thus, they highlight difficulties faced in the

formation and execution of digital marketing strategies, since the knowledge retained by the entrepreneur on each tool is reflected. The framework also demonstrated how small companies execute their digital marketing strategies, and what is the role of knowledge of tools and metrics in their use.

Regarding catastrophes of different orders, mainly environmental, climatic and geological in origin, it is demanding to think of solutions that help not only in the recovery of local businesses, but also of the region's environment and ecosystem, giving rise, many times, to ecological enterprises. So, the article "Which Speedboat will I go with? The Case of Passeio na Ilha da Restinga ", by Yuri Limeira Magalhães and Diana Lucia Teixeira de Carvalho, brings the discussion on marketing decisions and management actions, regarding eco-tourism contexts, helping managers to understand the possible paths for tourism organizations based on eco-tourism.

With the articles mentioned, we hope to contribute to organizations mobilizing their efforts to promote entrepreneurial responses to catastrophic events and crisis situations, in the current and future contexts.

Entrepreneurial responses from society to catastrophic events and crisis situations

We seek to broaden the understanding of entrepreneurial responses to catastrophic events and crisis situations in view of the importance of the role of society, public policies, government and ecosystems, briefly addressing the main contributions of literature in this area.

From a broader scope, which emphasizes the role of social and behavioral sciences in society in general, the study by Bavel et al. (2020) presents a profound review of the cognitive and social processes, to which certain individuals are subject, in catastrophic events, in particular, that of the COVID-19 pandemic. The authors classified the analysis according to the perception of threats, the coping with stress, among other reactions, suggesting intervention actions by different individual in society, as a way of dealing with the situation. In addition, the authors also identify a range of themes and gaps with a relevant source of information for entrepreneurial and innovative actions, intending to generate different solutions and promote the alignment of human behavior with the recommendations of epidemiologists and public health experts.

Another highlighted study is that by Bennett and Nikolaev (2020) that show a set of infectious diseases which affect a nation and the needed abilities to undertake and innovate. Through data from 83 countries, the authors analyze the prevalence rates of infectious diseases and cultural values of Hofstede's individualism-collectivism dimension, presenting evidence about the process of socioeconomic interaction and the skills to prevent or encourage innovation. The emphasis is on the role of public agents and public policy makers, who must be aware of the negative impact of infectious diseases, such as the current COVID-19 pandemic.

Shepherd and Williams (2019) explore the extraordinary capacity for compassion unleashed for an enterprise to alleviate the suffering of the affected population. With the experience of catastrophic events and crisis situations, such as the fires which spread rapidly throughout the state of Victoria, in Australia, and the devastating earthquake that hit Haiti in 2010, the authors (Williams & Shepherd, 2016) highlight entrepreneurship-action, investigating how the local social entrepreneurs act as catalysts. Those entrepreneurs are leaders in their communities and are capable to mobilize the collective emotional energies in favor of the development of new institutional arrangements, which is necessary for communities affected by disasters.

Farny, Kibler and Down (2018) conducted similar research in post-earthquake Haitian communities, highlighting the leadership role played by local social entrepreneurs, who acted as community activists, creating new institutional ventures.

Finally, a recent study by Shepherd (2020) mentions some fundamental research assumptions, addressing new challenges, such as the assumption that the Schumpeterian entrepreneur is the main source of disruption and that this phenomenon occurs between long periods of stability. From this perspective, the entrepreneur is an exceptional individual, with an extraordinary combination of attitudes, experiences, motivations and cognitions. However, recent research (Dutta, 2016, 2019; Peredo & Chrisman, 2006; Peredo, Haugh, & McLean, 2018; Roundy, 2019) shows that entrepreneurs are common people who have done extraordinary things in the face of catastrophic events and crisis situations.

There are several examples, from the object of investigation to the applied methods, encompassed by more theoretical and purposeful works, such as the Theory of Companies, based on the community (Peredo & Chrisman, 2006), and the essay on the common community in organizations for social purposes (Peredo et al.,

2018). Moreover, there are more quantitative works, with large volumes of data, such as Dutta's studies (2016; 2019) on health communities and natural disasters (floods, forest fires, hurricanes, tornadoes, earthquakes and droughts).

Such research indicates that the capacity of a community for organization depends on the wealth of its repertoire of models of voluntary organization, reflected in the diversity and strength of its associations. However, that weakens the communities with high levels of residential segregation by race and income because, even in the face of widely shared problems, there is a lack of solutions.

In post-disaster and crisis situations, such as the pandemic we are currently experiencing, a great effort by entrepreneurs is necessary to prevent bankruptcies. The studies by Roundy (2019) and Bishop (2019) address an important path of research in the generation of solutions for the recovery of entrepreneurial ecosystems. Roundy (2019) researched the communities belonging to the city of Warren, in the State of Ohio (USA), and defines as the "champions" of the entrepreneurial ecosystem, that is, the community leaders who adopted economic, socio-cultural strategies, and discursive communities to revitalize a struggling local ecosystem. Bishop (2019), in turn, analyzed all districts in England, using a spatial economic model, finding a positive association between the ability of entrepreneurs to facilitate regional adaptation to economic crises and the size/diversity of knowledge local stocks. To this end, the authors used variables such as the birth rate of companies and the numbers of workers in knowledge-based industries.

In view of the studies highlighted here, which address the importance of entrepreneurial responses from society in facing catastrophic events and crisis situations, we present, in this edition, with the work entitled "Ecosystem of social innovation and the intensity levels of the entrepreneur's inter-sector partnerships social", by Rodrigo Luiz Morais-da-Silva, Andréa Paula Segatto, Ana Carolina Vilela de Carvalho and Gutemberg Ribeiro, empirical evidence of how ecosystems of social innovation can be strengthened by effective inter-sector partnerships.

Also considering the entrepreneurial responses of society to catastrophic events and crisis situations, this time applied to the creative industry, we present the work of a qualitative nature and anchored in the Theory of Experiential Learning (TAE), which investigates the "Entrepreneurial skills in the creative industry: means and learning needs of musicians", by Tatiane Brum de Oliveira Reis and Amarolinda Iara da Costa Zanela Klein. In order to clarify the learning process of musicians and how

entrepreneurial skills are developed in the creative industry, the authors intend to favor the establishment of public policies that support the reconstruction and development of entrepreneurial activities in local economies in post- crisis scenarios.

Final considerations

With this brief review of the main contributions of the literature on entrepreneurial responses to catastrophic events and crisis situations, both by individuals and organizations and by society, we conclude our reflections, providing examples and actions for the opening of new perspectives and different paths. In this edition, we hope to bring a light at the end of the tunnel, with solutions for this context of uncertainties and challenges.

This editorial opens up a range of options for future research and presents studies regarding entrepreneurship activities in Brazil. In addition, we present an international contribution, which explains “Why do competitors in the informal sector make it more difficult for formal entrepreneurs in some countries?” This informative essay by Colin Williams discusses little explored and understood aspects of the entrepreneurship literature, based on the analysis of different theories and on data from 31 countries in Latin America and the Caribbean. Thus, in addition to contributing to the expansion of studies on the topic, the ideas developed in the article are useful for the building of public policies to reduce competition in the informal sector.

Another great gain in this edition is the “Pensata”, by Marcos Hashimoto, entitled “Teaching cases in Entrepreneurship: giving life and meaning to learning”, which elucidates the construction of teaching cases, and encourages their use in classrooms. This use suggestion is mainly because the cases are real testimonies, experienced by entrepreneurs from different areas and based on the learned lessons.

With the contributions from the literature, the works presented, and the reflections suggested in this edition, we hope to provoke new perspectives and alternative perspectives, in order to explore more solutions to face catastrophic events and crisis situations, and to recover the affected businesses and communities.

References

- Bacq, S., Geohegan, W., Josefy, M., Stevenson, R., & Williams, T. A. (2020). The Covid-19 “Virtual Idea Blitz”: Marshaling social entrepreneurship to rapidly respond to urgent grand challenges. *Business Horizons*, 63(6), 705-723.
- Barata, R. C. B. (1987). Epidemias. *Caderno Saúde Pública*, 3(1), 9-15.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1590/S0102-311X1987000100002>
- Battisti, M., & Deakins, D. (2017). The relationship between dynamic capabilities, the firm’s resource base and performance in a post-disaster environment. *International Small Business Journal*, 35(1), 78-98.
- Bavel, J. J. *et al.* (2020). Using social and behavioural science to support COVID-19 pandemic response. *Nature Human Behavior*, 4(5), 460-471.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-020-0884-z>
- Bennett, D. L., & Nikolaev, B. (2020). Historical Disease Prevalence, Cultural Values, and Global Innovation. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1042258720914506>.
- Baker, T. and Nelson, R. E. (2005) ‘Creating Something from Nothing: Resource Construction through Entrepreneurial Bricolage’, *Administrative Science Quarterly* 50: 329–66.
- Bishop, P. (2019). Knowledge diversity and entrepreneurship following an economic crisis: an empirical study of regional resilience in Great Britain. *Entrepreneurship & Regional Development*, 31(5-6), 496-515.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/08985626.2018.1541595>
- Borges, L. M., Ferreira, J. S., & Rover, S. (2017). Divulgação de acidentes ambientais no Brasil: uma análise a partir de notícias de jornais de grande circulação. *RMC – Revista Mineira de Contabilidade*, 18(3), art. 1, 5-15.

- Bullough, A., & Renko, M. (2013). Entrepreneurial Resilience during Challenging Times. *Business Horizons*, 56(3), 343-50.
- Bullough, A., Renko, M., & Myatt, T. (2014). Danger Zone Entrepreneurs: The Importance of Resilience and Self-Efficacy for Entrepreneurial Intentions. *Entrepreneurship: Theory and Practice*. 38. 10.1111/etap.12006.
- Davidsson e Gordon (2016). Much ado about nothing? The surprising persistence of nascent entrepreneurs through macroeconomic crisis. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 40(4), 915-941.
- Doern, R., Williams, N., & Vorley, T. (2019). Special issue on entrepreneurship and crises: business as usual? An introduction and review of the literature. *Entrepreneurship & Regional Development*, 31(5-6), 400-412.
- Dutta, S. (2016). Creating in the Crucibles of Nature's Fury: Associational Diversity and Local Social Entrepreneurship after Natural Disasters in California, 1991-2010. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 62(3), 443-483. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0001839216668172>
- Dutta, S. (2019). Seeing parochially and acting locally: Social exposure, problem identification and social entrepreneurship. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 34(6), 105942. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusvent.2019.06.003>
- Farny, S., Kibler, E., & Down, S. (2018). Collective Emotions in Institutional Creation Work. *Academy of Management Journal*, 62(3), 765-799. <https://doi.org/10.5465/amj.2016.0711>
- Fong, C. M., & Luttmer, E. F. P. (2007). What determines giving to hurricane Katrina victims? Experimental evidence on income, race, and fairness. *NBER Working Papers 13219*. Cambridge, MA: National Bureau of Economic Research, Inc.

- Freitas, C. M., Barcellos, C., Asmus, C. I. R. F, Silva, M. A., & Xavier, D. R. (2019). Da Samarco em Mariana à Vale em Brumadinho: desastres em barragens de mineração e Saúde Coletiva. *Caderno de Saúde Pública*, 35 (5).
- Geroski, P. A., & Gregg, P. (1996). What makes firms vulnerable to recessionary pressures? *European Economic Review*, 40(3-5), 551-557.
- Gray, R., & Bebbington, J. (2001). *Accounting for the Environment*. London, UK: Sage.
- Hoang, H., & Gimeno, J. (2010). Becoming a founder: How founder role identity affects entrepreneurial transitions and persistence in founding. *Journal of Business Venturing*. 25 (1),41-53.
- Kuckertz, A. et al. (2020). Startups in times of crisis – A rapid response to the COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of Business Venturing Insights*, 13, e00169.
- Kwong, C. C. Y., Cheung, C. W. M., Manzoor, H., & Rashid, M. U. (2019). Entrepreneurship through Bricolage: a study of displaced entrepreneurs at times of war and conflict. *Entrepreneurship & Regional Development*, 31(5-6), 435-455.
- Lacaz, F. A. C., Porto, M. F. S., & Pinheiro, T. M. M. (2017). Tragédias brasileiras contemporâneas: o caso do rompimento da barragem de rejeitos de Fundão/Samarco. *Revista Brasileira de Saúde Ocupacional*, 42 (9), 1-12.
- Martelli, C. M. T. (1997). Dimensão Histórica das Epidemias. *Revista de Patologia Tropical*, 26(1), 1-8.
- Mata-Lima, H., Alvino-Borba, A., Pinheiro, A., Mata-Lima, A., & Almeida, J. A. (2013). Impactos dos desastres naturais nos sistemas ambiental e socioeconômico: o que faz a diferença? *Ambiente & Sociedade*, XVI (3), 45-64.

- McDonald, R. M., & Eisenhardt, K. M. (2019). Parallel play: Startups, nascent markets, and effective business-model design. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 65(2), 483-523.
- Mel, S., Mckenzie, D., & Woodruff, C. (2010). Enterprise recovery following natural disasters. *Policy Research Working Paper Series 5269*. The World Bank.
- Mithani, M. A. (2020). Adaptation in the face of the new normal. *Academy of Management Perspectives*. In-press. <https://doi.org/10.5465/amp.2019.0054>
- Muñoz, P. Kimmitt, J. Kibler, E., & Farny, S. (2019). Living on the slopes: Entrepreneurial preparedness in a context under continuous threat. *Entrepreneurship and Regional Development*, 31, 413-434.
- Nassif, V. M. J., Corrêam V. S., & Rossetto, D. E. (2020a). Estão os empreendedores e as pequenas empresas preparadas para as adversidades contextuais? Uma reflexão à luz da pandemia do covid-19. *Revista de Empreendedorismo e Gestão e Pequenas Empresas - REGEPE*, 9(3), I-XII.
- Nassif, V. M. J., Armando, E., & La Falce, J. L. (2020b). O Empreendedorismo e a Pequena Empresa no Contexto do Pós-Covid-19: Há Luz no Fim do Túnel. *Revista de Empreendedorismo e Gestão e Pequenas Empresas - REGEPE*, 9(3), I-VIII.
- Nelson, R., & Lima, E. (2020). Effectuations, social bricolage and causation in the response to a natural disaster. *Small Bus Econ*, 54, 721-750. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11187-019-00150-z>.
- Peredo, A. M., & Chrisman, J. J. (2006). Toward a Theory of Community-Based Enterprise. *Academy of Management Review*, 31(2), 309-328. <https://doi.org/10.5465/amr.2006.20208683>

- Peredo, A. M., Haugh, H. M., & McLean, M. (2018). Common property: Uncommon forms of prosocial organizing. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 33(5), 591-602. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusvent.2017.11.003>
- Pott, C. M., Estrela, C. C. (2017). Histórico ambiental: desastres ambientais e o despertar de um novo pensamento. *Estudos Avançados* 31 (89), pp.271-283, DOI: 10.1590/s0103-40142017.31890021
- Queiroz, R. S. (2004). As epidemias como fenômenos sociais totais: o surto de gripe espanhola. *Revista USP*, (63), 64-73.
- Reymen, I. M. M. J., Andries, P., Berends, H., Mauer, R., Stephan, U., & Van Burg, E. (2015). Understanding dynamics of strategic decision making in venture creation: A process study of effectuation and causation. *Strategic Entrepreneurship Journal*, 9(4), 351-379. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sej>.
- Rosen, G. (1994). *Uma História da Saúde Pública*. São Paulo, Rio de Janeiro: Hucitec, Unesp, Abrasco.
- Roundy, P. T. (2019). Back from the brink: The revitalization of inactive entrepreneurial ecosystems. *Journal of Business Venturing Insights*, 12, e00140. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbvi.2019.e00140>.
- Sarasvathy SD, Dew N, Read S, Wiltbank R. (2008). Designing organizations that design environments: lessons from entrepreneurial expertise. *Organization Studies*;29(3):331-350.
doi:10.1177/0170840607088017
- Shepherd, D. A. (2020). COVID-19 and entrepreneurship: Time to pivot? *Journal of Management Studies*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/joms.12633>

- Shepherd, D. A., & Williams, T. A. (2018). Hitting rock bottom after job loss: Bouncing back to create a new positive work identity. *Academy of Management Review*, 43(1), 28-49.
- Shepherd, D. A., & Williams, T. A. (2019). *Spontaneous Venturing: An Entrepreneurial Approach to Alleviating Suffering in the Aftermath of a Disaster*. Cambridge, Massachusetts; London, England: The MIT Press. <https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/11470.001.0001>
- Silveira, A. J. T. (2005). A medicina e a influenza espanhola de 1918. *Tempo*, 10(19),91-105. <https://doi.org/10.1590/S1413-77042005000200007>
- Smallbone, D., Kitching, J., Kasperova, E., & Xheneti, M. (2013). A longitudinal analysis of small firm responses to the 2008-9 economic downturn. *ICSB World Conference Proceedings*, 2(2), 1-25. <https://search.proquest.com/docview/1617795230?pq-origsite=gscholar>
- Williams, T. A., & Shepherd, D. A. (2016). Building Resilience or Providing Sustenance: Different Paths of Emergent Ventures in the Aftermath of the Haiti Earthquake. *Academy of Management Journal*, 59(6), 2069-2102. <https://doi.org/10.5465/amj.2015.0682>
- Williams, T. A., Gruber, D. A., Sutcliffe, K. M., Shepherd, D. A., & Zhao, E. Y. (2017). Organizational response to adversity: Fusing crisis management and resilience research streams. *Academy of Management Annals*, 11(2), 733-769.
- Williams, T. A., & Shepherd, D. A. (2020). Bounding and binding: Trajectories of community-organization emergence following a major disruption. *Organization Science*. Forthcoming.
- Zissimopoulos, J., & Karoly, L. A. (2010). Employment and self-employment in the wake of Hurricane Katrina. *Demography*, 47, 345-367. <https://doi.org/10.1353/dem.0.0099>

